

STAGING THE TAREK DANCE: A VEHICLE FOR INTEGRATING THE INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE OF PALA'WAN INTO PHYSICAL EDUCATION CURRICULUM

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 2

Pages: 206-216

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2048

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12750744

Manuscript Accepted: 06-10-2024

Staging the Tarek Dance: A Vehicle for Integrating the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Pala'wan into Physical Education Curriculum

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Abstract

The preservation and promotion of the Indigenous communities' cultural heritage have been a long endeavor of many advocates from across the globe to lessen the possibility of losing it in the future. Thus, without the written documentation of the Tarek dance of the Pala'wan community in Barangay Bulalacao, Bataraza, Palawan, the researcher conducted descriptive research in the barangay. The data collected from the observation and interview among the Pala'wan elders were transcribed and analyzed through framework analysis. Tarek is a stamping dance on a bamboo floor, making a beautiful and synchronous sound with the Basal (the music produced by the percussion instruments), with common steps, namely, taptap, baw'bawi, and sinaraksakan. Furthermore, two sample lesson plans for teaching Tarek in Physical Education among grades 4 and 7 were proposed. The conclusions drawn in this study suggest the conduct of Pala'wan-led seminar-training workshops organized by the concerned units for teachers, dance enthusiasts, and other groups, a field testing of the sample lesson plans, and cultural mapping in other barangays of Bataraza, Palawan.

Keywords: *intangible cultural heritage, indigenous, Pala'wan, folk dance, staging, Physical Education*

Introduction

Cultural heritage, be it tangible or intangible, has been advocated for preservation and promotion over a long time (UNESCO, 1978; Atalan, 2018; Rouhi, 2017; Su, 2018; and Su et al., 2020). Although its concept may have been re-imagined from various disciplines (Bitusikova, 2021; Kim et al., 2019; Stocker & Deogracias, 2021; Zouni, 2019; and Patterson et al., 2018), Article 2 of Republic Act 10066 in the Philippines, known as the "National Cultural Heritage Act of 2009", could argue that the Indigenous Knowledge and Practices Systems (IKSP) of the Indigenous People (IPs), are among the numerous examples of intangible cultural heritage (ICH).

IPs in the country are composed of an estimated range from 10% to 20% of the total population (Eduardo & Gabriel, 2021), and they are not just owners of ICH but are responsible for acknowledging, regulating, safeguarding, and enhancing their possessions (Carril, 2016; Nyororo, 2018; Wheeler & Root-Bernstein, 2020; and Republic Act No. 8371). These groups are located in different regions of the country and are known for their cultural beliefs and traditions. Some were able to pass on and preserve their distinct customs and practices with the help of the national government (section 17 of Article XIV of the 1987 Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines) and private individuals like Francisca Reyes Aquino for Folk dance (Patrick, 2014).

Aquino aimed at promoting and conserving these folk dances for posterity since folk dance is widely recognized for its ability to embody a nation's diverse cultural heritage and is known for a wide variety of national elements (Buedron, 2017; Santos, 2019). Consequently, Aquino's scholarly contributions to Philippine folk dance have garnered the attention of fellow academics and have been incorporated into current educational curricula.

However, despite the protective actions taken by the government and private entities worldwide to protect the ICH, particularly in folk dances, certain customs and traditions are at risk of disappearing, with some already being lost due to various factors, including globalization, modernization, lack of engagement among younger generations, and practitioners' mortality (Kockar et al., 2004 and Besmonte, 2022).

In light of this, numerous published works on folk dance from the province of Palawan in the Philippines have already gained national recognition. For instance, the Kender Dance (Alabi, 2021) and the Basal (Cansino, 2019) of the Pala'wan from Quezon and Rizal, respectively.

The Pala'wan Indigenous Community is mainly located in the southern part of Palawan, Philippines, and includes Rizal, Bataraza, Brooke's Point, Balabac, Sofrono Espanola, and Quezon. Thus, the dances of the Pala'wan mentioned above are undoubtedly a source of pride for the entire Pala'wan community.

Noticeably, unlike the Kender, neither the movements nor the melody of either Basal (Tarek or sapa sapa) has been recorded. At the same time, the existing research on Basal Ritual, where sacred practices and non-sacred dance are usually performed, excludes interviews and participating observation with the community as collection methods.

Apparently, the researcher was unable to locate any mention of the community of Bataraza in the research projects of Kender and Basal in Quezon and Rizal, despite the potential impact of the previously discussed losing factors on the cultural practices of the IPs. Since the researcher was born and raised in the municipality of Bataraza and considered herself an advocate of culture, she conducted a preliminary investigation with Pala'wan members in the municipality. Through this attempt, she learned about the ICH of barangay

Bulalacao, which might be similar to Rizal's basal ritual observed by Cansino (2019).

Engaging initially in dialogue with the community leads the researcher to acknowledge that the current methods of performance have undergone a possible transformation. Therefore, the researcher desires to consider supporting the community in preserving their heritage through documentation, hoping to help preserve the practice in such a way that it can be passed on to many generations and may still be understood within their original settings (Khan et al., 2018; Bamidele et al., 2022; Mezzino et al., 2017; and Akhtar et al., 2017); proper preservation that would entail accurate dance properties (Castaños, 2022) and other significant elements (Giannoulakis et al., 2018 and Domingo's, 2018), that are also recommended by Villacrusis et al. (2021), Marquez (2005), and No & Esguerra (2023). In contrast, Oruc (2022) emphasized that there is more possibility for varying interpretations and bias, especially when collecting ICH, since scholars may practice them differently.

Furthermore, the researcher has also realized that Tarek is not included in the Physical Education (PE) curriculum despite its cultural significance, considering that the school is located in the same municipality where the Pala'wan community also lives. Following a curriculum review, it has been observed that the educational resources related to dance can be modified to better align with regional circumstances, which provides a significant impact on students and the potential revitalizing the promotion of authentic folk dances (Asuncion & Labaguis, 2022; Cos, 2021; and Evina; 2023), provided PE teachers know how to teach it authentically by following the dance literature, performance, appropriate staging, and visual impact Garcia (2020).

Finally, the lack of available resources for integrating local dances (Domingo, 2018) also motivates the researcher to pursue this study further.

Research Questions

This qualitative study aimed to document the trek dance of the Pala'wan residing in barangay Bulalacao, Bataraza, Palawan. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is Tarek dance?
2. What are the dance elements of Tarek?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative research methodology, specifically a descriptive case study approach. According to Creswell, as cited by Priya (2021), case studies allow researchers to thoroughly investigate a program, event, activity, process, or one or more individuals. Specifically, the descriptive type of a case study aims to provide a comprehensive depiction of a phenomenon within its authentic, real-world setting in which researchers may gather detailed information using various data collection methods. This approach was appropriate as it allowed the researcher to document the practices of the Pala'wan community in performing the Tarek dance.

Participants

The study was conducted in the Municipality of Bataraza, located in the Province of Palawan, Philippines. However, the study mainly focused on the Pala'wan community in the barangay of Bulalacao, which has been recognized for its longstanding and consistent tradition of performing the Tarek dance. Meanwhile, the Pala'wan community leaders themselves selected the participants to be interviewed and observed; however, guided with the following criteria developed by Tremblay, as cited by Marquez (2005): [1] Role in the Community, [2] Knowledge and [3] Willingness. Hence, a total of 12 elders served as the participants.

Procedure

Before the actual data-gathering process, the researcher sought permission from the authorities. Upon approval of the requests and issuance of the necessary permits, the researcher conducted observation as per the schedule agreed between the community and the researcher. The observation was made to witness the authentic way of performing the Basal, particularly the Tarek, as it yields advantages under specific circumstances (Seim, 2021).

Secondly, the researcher interviewed 12 Pala'wan participants to discover more about the significance, history, and elements of Tarek dance and how the community wanted it to be staged. The interview guide questions were adapted from the handbook of Castanos (2021), which provided sample questions for dance participants. However, validation from three experts in the field was performed since modifications were employed.

Data Analysis

The initial step of the study was to document the Tarek dance through observations and interviews, which generated observation field notes and the participants' narratives. In this phase, the researcher processed and analyzed these data using framework analysis. This type of analysis entails immersing oneself in data and drawing conclusions in order to identify, demonstrate, and explain key patterns and themes within and across instances of the studied phenomenon (Goldsmith, 2021). In particular, the data were processed and analyzed through the following five steps: [1] Data familiarization, [2] Identifying a thematic framework, [3] Indexing all study data

against the framework, [4] Charting to summarize the indexed data, and [5] Mapping and interpretation.

Ethical Considerations

The University Ethics Review Committee approved the study protocol, and the researcher strictly adhered to Section 8.1 of NCIP Administrative Order No. 1 series of 2012, The Indigenous Knowledge Systems and Practices (IKSPs) and Customary Laws (CLs) Research and Documentation Guidelines of 2012.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Tarek of the Pala'wan*

Themes	Sub-themes
The Beginning	From God, Ancestors, and Parents. Composed by Balyan.
Nature of the Dance	Purpose of Tarek. The Traditional way. Women Dancers.
Dance Elements	Steps and Styling. Movement of Arms. Formation and Direction. Clothes, Costume. Props. Accessory. Music.
Staging	Traditional. Alternatives

Table 1 shows the themes (left column) and the sub-themes (right column) that were established from the data analysis, which sought to answer the following questions: (1) what is tarek? and (2) what are the dance elements of tarek?

Theme 1. The Beginning

The finding from table 5 shows that most of the Pala'wan participants do not know exactly how the dance tarek started; however, they expressed their belief that it existed even before they were born as they grew up observing it or doing it with their parents, stating it was also passed down to their parents by their ancestors. Moreover, it is also believed to be a gift from God. Some participants said;

"It was from our ancestors."

(Nanggaling daw sa ninuno namin, p1)

"For me, I do not know that anymore except for the elders who came before us."

(Kasi kung para saakin hindi na natin alam yon ma'am, kundi sa mga naumang matatanda pa, p8)

"Maybe it was given to us by God for women."

(Bigay na lang ba siguro ng panginoon kasi para may(roon) kay babae, p11)

On the other hand, few of the Pala'wan believe that it was composed by a Balyan, a powerful elder in their community, also known as a village elder, so women can enjoy the night after others have performed a sacred ritual. At the same time, the Balyan composed the dance to accompany the instruments being played since the musicians have to play them throughout the night. A participant told;

"The Balyan said, if you want to have fun (after turon), do the tarek dance. If you do not know, just follow me. So, it seems like it was just composed by a Balyan."

(Ayan na rin yong balyan na yan sabi niya kung magkasiyahan kayo mag tarek kayo. Sabi hindi namin alam, sabi gayahin ninyo. Parang kinompos kompos lang ba, p12)

Theme 2. Nature of Dance

The term "tarek" may not have a direct translation, the participants describe the it as literally "to stamp or step heavily," "to dance," and "to have fun."

Tarek is originally performed in a big house with an allotted area for gathering, called kelang banwa. As explained, the owners of the big houses are the ones who commonly call for a gathering. The houses of the Pala'wan are apart from one another, but they manage to make it to the big houses through oral transition since the elders had the chance to discuss and schedule the next ones from the previous gathering. Thus, people are informed when and where to go next. Moreover, the sound of the gongs and other musical instruments is played and intentionally performed a few hours before the ritual at night so that people can hear it and learn that the ritual is about to begin, which the researcher has also observed. Nowadays, the participants acknowledged the shift in its term from big house or kelang banwa to a bahay tarukan.

In any gathering, the Pala'wan emphasized that tarek is observed only after performing turon, a sacred ritual for healing and thanksgiving activities. More specifically, turon is performed whenever they make rice wine called simbog, purad, and tabad and during the offering for the blessings they received from God, known as sidang. As said;

"When they were making what they called tabad (wine). That was when they made rice into rice wine. It takes about a month or two months. We would do that every night (the ritual and tarek)."

(Pag naga, yong sabi nila nagagawa ng tabad. Yong ginagawa na alak na palay (bigas). Isang buwan o dalawang buwan. Gabi gabi yan, p2)

"We will commence Sidang, an offering, which is why there will be turon (sacred ritual)."

(Mag sidang kaya yan mag turon, Mag alay ba., p2)

A balyan leads this sacred ritual, commonly lasting until the middle of the night. Only then will the tarek be performed by women. Participants explained:

"Our elders used to forbid us from performing tarek, "your grandfather had not yet performed turon."

(Binabawalan kami ng matatanda namin noon na wag muna mag tarek, hindi pa naka turon lolo mo, p1)

"We will perform turon first."

(Yong turon pa muna saamin, p10)

According to the participants, tarek is primarily performed to keep the people alive and happy throughout the night after performing the said ritual. Thus, this dance showcases heavy steps on the bamboo floor of a house. Heavy steps are played to produce loud sounds and prevent people from becoming sleepy. In this sense, the elders revealed that the transition from turon to tarek starts by striking silad leaves on the floor to serve its purpose. They stated;

"Of course, some people, when turon is over, [tarek] will help them not to fall asleep. Because if there is no tarek, what else is there to watch for."

(Syempre yong iba kasi pag tapos na ang turon, yan na para hindi lang makatulog. Kasi kung wala ng tarek, syempre ano pang bantayan, p2)

"And for the musicians not to fall asleep, because they were enjoying the tarek."

(Tyaka para di makatulog yong manig tugtog kasi nasasayahan sila sa tarek, p5)

"Because if no one performs tarek, then there is nothing, and playing music isn't enjoyable either."

(Kasi kung wala yong mag tarek, wala rin, hindi rin nasasayahan mag tugtog, p4)

To begin the dance, elders mentioned that women would line up to organize their entry to the bamboo floor's center and avoid collisions. Some dancers can rest or sleep at the side when they get tired. However, other dancers must stay on the dance floor to accompany the music. A short break is also observed so they can drink and eat for a while. However, musicians can be seen resting only for a little less moment compared to the dancers.

Children and other women are also welcome to participate. From what has been observed, even those who do not know how to do tarek steps can try. Per the interview, men also can participate, although this scene was not witnessed during the observation. One participant said;

"Just the women and even children can join. But now men also join."

(Babae lang. Kahit bata pwede rin. Pero ngayon naka halo halo na yong lalaki, p10)

However, most men refused to join since it usually does not please the eyes of the elders, according to the participants. For instance, one male participant expressed;

"Men can't join; it looks bad"

(Hindi ba pwede maám kung lalaki. Pangit tingnan, p8)

The elders also shared stories about the competitions, challenges, and teasing moments between the musicians and the dancers, especially from late night to dawn. First, they are betting on which group to give up: the musicians or dancers. Second, the musicians change the tempo of the music to make it even faster to challenge the dancers. On the other hand, dancers would call the attention of the musicians and tease them whenever they do not like their play. As a result, they would stop and reset the playing of instruments while both groups would laugh at each other.

Ultimately, the Pala'wan explained that tarek usually ends between 6 and 7 in the morning through agreement, without any consequence to whoever surrenders first. Notably, the ending point of tarek is when one or both groups surrender, get tired, or give way to doing other activities.

Theme 3. Dance Elements

Steps and Styling

There are three different steps identified, namely taptap, baw'bawi, and sinaraksakan.

Taptap is the slowest step among the three, and it is the easiest as well. Some participants often need to pay more attention to this step when performing. The elders explained that this is a routine observed during the first entry of the dancers on the dance floor to immerse oneself in music and to keep up with it correctly. With that sense, expert dancers often skip this part.

The second step is moderately fast. It is known as baw'bawi by the elders. However, the description of this step can be deceiving since most participants prefer the other steps to this routine. According to them, they do not know how to do it properly. However, two of them were able to demonstrate it during the interview. Baw'bawi has a sudden stop-of-steps technique, which can not be seen in the first step discussed earlier.

Like taptap, sinaraksakan does not need a sudden stop in steps. However, it is considered the fastest step by the participants. Among all of these, this is their favorite step to execute, even when they are performing the dance in public programs in the municipality or other places.

Furthermore, regardless of the chosen steps, each step must be executed as intensely as possible to produce a loud yet synchronous sound with the music. However, no counting was observed in executing these steps.

Movements of Arms

As observed and per the interview, arm movements are called siboy. Siboy is the term used by the participants to describe how they execute the arm movements for tarek. Basically, siboy means simultaneous or synchronous, reiterating that the dancers' arms shall ideally move as one. Moreover, it was emphasized that hands, when moving, should not go beyond the shoulder level, while elbows are usually close to the side of the body. Common arm movements are (1) swaying up and down at the side and (2) swaying to the front-side-down, creating a circular motion.

Props

During the dance performance, dancers must hold a set or a piece of dried silad leaves per hand. As explained, this is a must during tarek to avoid getting possessed by evil spirits or getting sick. As mentioned earlier, tarek is performed right after a sacred ritual, and believed that spirits are still around during this time.

Figure 1. Dried Silad Leaves (The researcher took this photo)

Silad is also known as wild anahaw (palm tree) among the Pala'wan. They preferably get the leaves that have not bloomed yet (as in Figure 2-B). Then, the leaves will be torn apart into pieces and curled (as in Figure 2) to make a volume before they get dry.

Figure 2. *Silad Trees*

Formation and Direction

The elders also emphasized the formation and directions of the dancers for this dance. In particular, dancers shall line up to create a single line, with the first dancer in front facing the center. If other dancers can not line up due to limited space, they may wait in different areas of the house until the line becomes short.

When ready to dance, dancers may enter solo, by pair, or by group. However, it is observed that a pair or group of dancers should enter in a particular order, by which the first dancer should enter first before being followed by another and another again. Subsequent dancers should position just behind the dancer they follow, maintaining a single line.

These dancers may move counterclockwise to create a single circle, a common formation for a group, aside from a single line. When solo or by pair, it is observed that dancers may explore any direction on the dance floor, yet keeping the dancers' sequence in the line, with a dancer in front leading.

When exiting, it should always be at the left side or to the left then to the back. A pair or group dancers may exit simultaneously or one at a time at, provided that whoever is left at the very front should take the lead and must be followed by the others to keep the line. Strictly, the elders emphasize that following a dancer in line includes following the steps and movements she is executing. This way, the elders expressed their satisfaction on how it would work well to avoid trouble among the dancers and trouble with the formations and the sound it would produce.

Clothing or Costumes

Meanwhile, the dancers wear sablay and patadyong, while a loincloth or bahag is worn by musicians, replacing the wood-made clothing of their ancestors. Some of them could wear wood-made clothes, but most of them grew up wearing the former. Sablay is a long-sleeve-buttoned top cloth with glittery lines or gems in the middle, while patadyong is used to make a skirt by wrapping or tying it around the waist.

Figure 3. *Sablay and Patadyong*

Accessory

A long necklace made of natural beads is used as an accessory. It is commonly made of manas or dalas, which are vegetation. However, their clothing and accessories are noticeably changing as well. In point of fact, only one of the participants was able to show a manas with natural beads. Furthermore, the participants revealed that synthetic beaded-necklace are also used nowadays

Figure 4. Manas

Musical Instruments

The music, called Basal, is produced by playing percussion instruments, namely gimbal, sanang, and gong, usually one, two, and two in quantity, respectively. As told by them, the music, precisely the tempo of the gimbal, is the basis of the dancers in executing the steps, emphasizing that they do not use exact step counting. However, each instrument plays a significant role in playing Basal, the tarek dance's music. Unfortunately, it is noticed that the community only uses an empty gallon in place of the actual gimbal. The elders explained that it is hard to have a real gimbal nowadays, which is supposedly made of wood and the skin of a goat on top, since even the skin of a goat is often served on the table for consumption.

Figure 13. Gongs

Figure 14. Sanang

Figure 15. The alternative gimbal (plastic containers)

Staging the Dance

Performing the dance in a different platform for staging purposes should follow the typical procedure of the Pala'wan in this barangay. The participants or the elders strongly expressed their desire to witness the staging of tarek as traditional as possible. However, even though it is commonly performed after a turon, excluding this sacred ritual in a show is a must, emphasizing that tarek alone is acceptable for staging. For instance, the participants explained;

"We have to do it properly, just as we used to."

(Kailangan itama natin sa nagisingan namin, p1)

"But ma'am, to be honest, when it's mixed up, tarek and turon, it's not possible."

(Pero ma'am sa totoo lang kapag halo, sayaw tyaka turon, yan ang hindi pwede, p6)

On the other hand, alternative props are acceptable for staging in place of materials that can not be brought on stage or are hard to produce anymore—for instance, the use of lantay in the absence of a natural bamboo floor of a house. Lantay is a portable floor made of tied bamboo as if it were a bamboo floor of a typical kelang banwa. In addition, synthetic necklaces, any long-sleeve tops, and other types of long skirts may also be used for staging. Participants said;

"When staged, it's okay to make a portable bamboo floor, just laying it out."

(Kapag ipalabas, okay lang na yong ginagawa lang na kawayan. Yong nilalata lang, p5)

"[If there are no manas], it is okay to use fruit or beads from other plants that can be seen on the riverbanks."

(kung walang manas) Yong bungang kahoy daw mam na makikita sa mga tabing ilog, p6)

While the beginning is unknown to many, which raises some concerning issues regarding the transmission of the tradition, it was observed from the participants how invested they were in sharing their knowledge about it. With this regard, only a few believed it started with the inventive mind of the Balyan, who composed the steps of tarek. This revelation may need to be more evident to prove its actual beginning; however, it makes sense with the study of Cansino (2019) with the Pala'wan in the municipality of Rizal, narrating that a Balyan leads a ritual. Despite this, the lack of knowledge on the history of dance by many is comparable with the study of Belmonte (2022), wherein the death of the ancestors or practitioners is a factor in losing the tradition. In this sense, the passing of knowledgeable ancestors implies a failure to transmit information to the next generations fully. In light thereof, the dance's continued existence to date indicates the effort of the community to keep the culture alive. It implies that the Pala'wan still upholds on to keeping the tradition for the next generations.

As the researcher tried to explore the nature of tarek dance, it was observed that the practices of the Pala'wan are not just simply a part of their daily lives but also reflect their way of life. It supports the research of Cansino (2019), Sinag (2022), and Belmonte (2022) that the traditional activities of the Indigenous people mirror their identity. For instance, it illustrates the cheerful and dedicated nature of the tarek dancers despite the energy and time demands of the dance. On a more serious note, it plays a crucial role in fostering strong relationships among community members by providing opportunities to spend time together and engage in conversations.

Furthermore, although tarek is not part of their sacred ritual and is considered a less serious tradition, the elders still show respect and value by following what their parents taught them—for instance, discouraging drunk individuals and others wearing pants from participating. On the other hand, the Pala'wan community still demonstrates its inclusive nature by welcoming children and others to join in the tarek dance. Involving children in this tradition implies learning and developing skills crucial to preserving this traditional dance. Encouraging the younger generation to actively observe and participate in the dance is essential for passing down cultural values and promoting solidarity within the community. This also implies that Pala'wan elders do not simply perform the dance; they also create opportunities for everyone, including the children, to have fun, get along, and participate in the tradition.

Finally, the participants expressed enthusiasm and eagerness to share the dance with the public. Their agreement to stage the dance reflects their commitment to promoting it and increasing its recognition. In a broader sense, the desire of the participants to stage it as traditionally as possible reflects not just promotion but preservation. Absolor et al. (2023) also observed the same approach in other communities in the country, wherein IPs continue to aspire to preserve their traditions despite threats. However, reiterating the study of Bitusikova (2021), which explained that cultural heritage may be modified once publicized, sparks a sense of wonder and opens up the possibility of affecting the concept of preservation that the community desires. Thus, Arendt and Jeudy by Marinescu (2021) describes action today toward heritage as not just about preserving history. However, it is also about fighting against the cultural crisis that modernity has unleashed. This implies a risk of misinterpretation and alterations; thus, sensitive promotion to the public and proper dissemination of knowledge and skills are crucial in addressing this concern.

Conclusions

The findings confirmed that tarek is an intangible cultural heritage of the Pala'wan in the barangay of Bulalacao that is believed to be a gift from God through a Balyan. It is not easy to arrive at any conclusions about its actual beginning. However, the elders aspire to keep it preserved for the present and future generations by practicing and showing it to the younger generations up to date.

In addition, the findings provided that Tarek is a traditional activity that women usually perform in the middle of the night during special occasions. It serves as an opportunity for people to gather together for social and entertainment purposes. This conclusion follows from the fact that it is traditionally performed after a sacred and more serious ritual called turon.

It would appear that although tarek does not follow a strict codified sequence of steps, the dancers must observe a single line and circle going counterclockwise while demonstrating steps of their choice—taptap, sinaraksakan, and baw'bawi. The dancers must synchronously demonstrate the steps with the music called basal. Meanwhile, the dancers wear Patadyong and Sablay, a beaded long necklace, and hold Silad leaves (wild palm) in both hands.

In staging the dance, this paper argued that although some alterations are visibly observed through time, the public must showcase its traditional way as the elders. In this sense, promoting dance information through documentation and disseminating it to the public,

particularly in elementary and secondary schools, must follow the community's desire by staging it in a culturally relevant manner.

Therefore, it is recommended to organize a seminar training and workshop for the teachers, cultural advocates, and other concerned groups, with the presence of the Pala'wan community at barangay Bulalacao, particularly the tarek dancers, as trainers, to learn the dance firsthand from them and to honor the community where the dance belongs, conduct field testing for the elementary and secondary school lesson plans, and initiate more documentation or research on the cultural heritage in the country.

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